

Population Health in Northern Mozambique. The Civil Society Opinion: A Qualitative Study

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Abstract

Context: The Government of Mozambique, responding to Islamic insurgency since 2017, aiming to design a resilience strategy in Northern Mozambique (Cabo Delgado, Nampula and Niassa provinces), asked Lúrio University in 2021 to perform a consultation with grassroots communities in civil society and internally displaced people, to assess their health situation, needs and proposals.

Materials and Methods: Qualitative descriptive study with focus groups discussions in urban, rural, inland, and coastal communities and internally displaced people, respecting ethical, safety, confidentiality, and preventive measures of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. Convenience sampling was determined in each community and participants were selected with the support of local leaders, focusing on "resource people", stratified by adults' gender and youth. Demographic and social data were analysed with SPSS software and answers to health questions were collected in writing and dealt with discourse analysis by category and subcategory. Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study.

Findings: A total of 54 focus group discussions were held with 320 participants, 47.5% female, 65.6% adult and 34.4% adolescent and youth, 23.8% internally displaced persons. Most families recognise the importance of the national health service but feel cheated by the widespread corruption in public services, COVID-19 pandemic, and insurgency.

Conclusion: The grassroots communities of the three provinces of northern Mozambique face daily challenges to their livelihoods and consider that public services and external support are insufficient. Valuing the availability of a free national health service, they point out serious limitations in these services, but also some proposals for solutions.

Introduction

In 2017, the population of the northern region of Mozambique was close to 10 million inhabitants, with high population growth rates since 2007, in the provinces of Niassa (49.2%), Nampula (41.9%) and Cabo Delgado (28.4%) [1]. These communities are mostly in a situation of social and economic vulnerability, with a lack of infrastructure [2], despite the vast natural resources of the region (precious stones, graphite, natural gas, forests, wildlife) [3,4]. The occurrence of natural disasters, frequent in Mozambique and aggravated by climate and human catastrophes (crime, smuggling, violent conflicts) [5-8], have caused the destruction of public and private property, the closure of public services and businesses, the abandonment of schools and health centres, unemployment and the displacement of more than 1.2 million people [9,10].

To overcome this crisis, the Government of Mozambique (GM), through the Ministry of Agriculture and Local Development, requested the support of the United Nations (UN), the European Union (EU), the World Bank (WB) and the African Development Bank (AfDB), to design a strategy aimed at promoting development and resilience in Northern Mozambique, to be implemented by the Northern Integrated Development Agency [11].

The Centre for Environmental Research and Conservation of Lúrio University (UniLúrio), located in the city of Pemba, capital of Cabo Delgado province, was invited to carry out a study in civil society grassroots communities and with internally displaced persons (IDPs), to assess, prioritize and validate the feelings, grievances and needs of these populations in

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the humanitarian sphere, development, and the reconstruction of peace.

This study goal was to assess, prioritize, and validate the health situations and needs of civil society grassroots communities, including IDPs, in Cabo Delgado, Nampula, and Niassa provinces.

Materials and Methods

This is a qualitative descriptive study to assess the health situation with focus groups discussions (FGD). The data collection instrument was tested and validated in Portuguese and Makua (the main local language). Convenience sampling was determined in different types of communities (urban, rural, inland, coastal, IDPs) and participants were selected with the support of local administrative, traditional, and religious leaders, focusing on "resource people" (opinion leaders, traditional and religious, formal, and informal entrepreneurs, civil servants and employees, traditional health practitioners - THP, students), stratified by adults' gender and youth (18 to 24 years old). Two FGDs were carried out for each stratum in each of the nine selected communities (see chart 1). The FGDs were authorized by the local and provincial administrative authorities, took place privately for two hours, between the 20th and 30th of July 2021, carried out by four teams of three trained UniLúrio researchers, accredited, unknown to the participants, respecting the ethical, safety and confidentiality recommendations, as well as the preventive measures of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study and all participants signed an informed consent form. Written notes were taken, and no audiovisual recordings were made. Discussions were conducted in local languages, noted by two investigators, and notes checked by a third investigator. Demographic and social variables, as well as the answers to the questions under study, were collected. The data were treated with *Microsoft Office Word* and *Excel* and the bias was controlled by triangulation of researchers for data quality assurance. Demographic and social data were analysed in the *SPSS21* software to determine frequencies and

percentages, as well as discourse analysis of the issues under debate by category and sub-category.

After data collection, processing and analysis, the preliminary report was prepared and results were returned to the participants of the FGDs in the same communities, between October 14 and November 18, 2021, to collect their criticisms, addendums, and opinion on the study methods, observing all ethical guidelines, security and confidentiality and preventive measures against the Covid-19 pandemic. The feedback sessions took place presenting the data collected in the respective community regarding the issues under study, taking note of the participants' observations including important missing points or misinterpretations, new situations or events and appreciation of the research methods. The main findings coinciding in the three provinces were presented, soliciting opinions on similarities and contrasts between the different communities. Research' purpose, interest and usefulness were explained, and voluntary participation was thanked. Chart 2 details feedback sessions participants. This activity corresponded to participants' requests in FGDs regarding information about study results and purpose, constituting a method of bias correction by triangulation of data with the participants.

As study limitations we point out some participants' mental health derangements (post-traumatic stress) that partially limited information collection with IDPs, and logistical and internal organizational difficulties that altered the feedback plan, delaying activities, limiting the number of participants, given the existence of groups with significant residential mobility (farmers, students, merchants).

Results

A total of 54 FGDs were carried out with 320 participants, 152 (47.5%) females and 168 (52.5%) males, 210 (65.6%) adults and 110 (34.4%) adolescents and young people, 76 (23.8%) IDPs. The mean age of men was 37 years (20 for young people and 45 for adults), for women 41 years (20 for young women, 46 for adults).

Table 1: Participants in Focus Group Discussions

Province	Community	Adults		Young		Total
		Women	Men	Women	Men	
Cabo Delgado	Pemba Christian Church	16	8	5	8	37
	Islamic Church of Pemba	14	11	7	5	37
	Miners of Montepuez	14	10	1	13	38
	IDPs in Chiure	11	12	6	7	36
Total CD	4	55	41	19	33	148
Nampula	IDPs in Corane	15	13	5	7	40
	Fishermen of Nacala	11	12	2	11	36
	Islamic of Mozambique island	11	12	4	6	33
Total Na	3	37	37	11	24	109
Niassa	Rural of Niassa Reserve	10	10	5	6	31

	Urban of Sanga	10	10	5	7	32
Total Ni	2	20	20	10	13	63
TOTAL	9	112	98	40	70	320
Total F:						152
Total M:						168

Note: CD – Cabo Delgado province; Na – Nampula province; Ni – Niassa province; F – Female; M – Male.

Nine meetings were held for data retrieval with 195 participants, 47% female and 53% male, 63% adults and 37% adolescents and young people, 21% IDPs.

Table 3 summarizes participants’ social characteristics.

Table 2: Participants in Feedback Sessions

Province	Community	Adults		Young	Total
		Women	Men	F/M	
CD	Pemba Christian Church	6	8	5	19
CD	Islamic Church of Pemba	5	9	8	22
CD	Miners of Montepuez	3	8	6	17
CD	PIDs in Chiure	7	5	16	28
Total CD	4	21	30	35	86
Na	PIDs in Corane	6	3	5	14
Na	Fishermen of Nacala	10	8	11	29
Na	Islamic of the Island of Mozambique	9	12	6	27
Total Na	3	25	23	22	70
Ni	Rural of the Niassa Reserve	2	3	11	16
Ni	Urban of Sanga	10	9	4	23
Total Ni	2	12	12	15	39
TOTAL	9	58	65	72	195

Note: F – Female; M – Male; CD – Cabo Delgado; NA – Nampula; NI - Niassa

Table 3: Focus Groups Discussions Participants’ Social Characteristics

Variable	Classification	Women (%)	Men (%)
Ethnic-linguistic group	Emakua	37.5	38.1
	Nahara	18.4	23.8
	Jawa	17.8	17.3
	Makonde	19.7	14.3
	Kimwani	5.3	6.6
Religion	Islam	64.2	67.7
	Christian	35.1	31.7
	No religion	0.7	0.6
Schooling	Illiterate	19.7	3.6
	Attended primary/secondary school	66.5	74.4
	Completed secondary education (12th grade)	13.2	19.0
	Have completed higher education	0.7	3.0
Occupation	Peasants	27.7	20.3
	Unemployed / unemployed	20.5	19.1
	Fishermen	0	16.1
	Students	12.2	9.5
	Traders	9.9	8.9
	Domestic	19.2	0
	Several	10.5	26.1
Marital status	Married	42.1	50.0
	Together (equated to married)	4.6	13.7
	Single	28.9	36.3
	Widowers	12.5	0
	Separate	7.2	0
	Divorced	4.6	0

Cabo Delgado Province

Christian community, city of Pemba: in the capital of Cabo Delgado province on the coast, the participants were mostly Emakua (69%), also Makonde, men and women with an average schooling of 10 years. Some defended the achievements of the GM, others complained about corruption in public services and their poor quality, suggesting training of health professionals (HPs), improvement of infrastructure and availability of quality medicines.

Women: average age of 50 years, most have a domestic occupation, some are already retired, and one was a civil servant. Most are widows, 4 married, 4 singles, 2 separated. They complain of chronic diseases and of not receiving good care in the national health service (NHS).

Youth: average age of 24 years and 11 of schooling, all girls have a domestic occupation, most boys study, few have another occupation (domestic, tailor, activist). All are single. They are in good health, but they feel that the abuse of alcohol and other drugs is increasing among young people.

Men: average age 53 years, 27% are civil servants, some retired (18%) and others unemployed (18%), most are single (73%), others married (27%). Mental health suffers due to Covid-19 and the problem of the arrival of many IDPs due to the conflict, victims of violence in a situation of post-traumatic stress and without psychological support.

"...we are all suffering from this issue of war, I received 32 people in my house, all of them from my family, who lived on these islands in the district of Palma, just imagine how I can feed all these people." (M, 39 years old).

They think that the GM must fight seriously against corruption, which is present in all public services.

Feedback: the 19 participants expressed satisfaction by confirming that their concerns and contributions were considered and appreciating their participation in the possible improvement of some services provided to the community. The group positively evaluated the study method and requested that research such as this one be developed more frequently, as the community has the freedom to express itself and be heard, unlike what happens with surveys, mostly with closed questions, which do not give space for discussion of other ideas that the community considers relevant.

Muslim community, city of Pemba: men and women with an average schooling of 13 years, 4 were graduates; most adults are married, others single or widowed. They were grateful for the free NHS but complained about corruption and the poor quality of public services.

Women: all belong to the Emakua ethnic group, with an average age of 52 years and 5 years of schooling, the

vast majority have a domestic occupation and are married, 1 is a civil servant (teacher), 3 are widows and 1 is divorced. They receive psychological support from religious leaders when needed, who now also support IDPs. Health is not well due to poor quality of water, food and medicines, poor care in the NHS and a poorly functioning referral system for critically ill patients.

Youth: average age of 20 years and 11 years of schooling, all of them of Emakua ethnicity, have always lived in Pemba; most of the girls are students, 1 shopkeeper and 1 domestic; half of the boys study, the others are traders. Most are single, 1 married boy, 2 separated girls and 1 widow. They mention the practice of illicit collections in the NHS.

"In maternity wards, the service is terrible, the midwives leave you rolling when your time to deliver the baby has come, just because you didn't give 500 Meticais – Mozambican coin" (F, 22 years old).

Men: mostly from the Emakua group (67%) but also Kimwani (33%), with an average age of 34 years and 13 years of education, have varied professions (accountant, teacher, theologian, technician); half are married and the others single, almost all born and residing in Pemba. They complain about poor service and corruption in the NHS.

Feedback: the 22 participants (64% male, 36% adolescents and young people) expressed satisfaction with results restitution, claiming that their contributions were well noted. The group positively evaluated the study method, considering that the participants have the freedom to express their feelings, voluntarily, safely and confidentially.

Community of informal miners in the village of Namanhumbir, district of Montepuez: rural inland village, 15 km from the city of Montepuez, district capital. Participants were all Emakua ethnicity, mostly Catholics, men, and women with an average schooling of 3 years, all adults live from subsistence agriculture; most of them are married or equivalent, there are also separated women.

Women: average age of 42 years and 3 years of schooling, all of them of Emakua ethnicity, two-thirds are Christians, and the rest are Muslim. All of them are peasants with no specific training, most of them married, 6 separated, mostly born, and living in this community. Health is not good, there is a lack of food and medicines, there are many new diseases; NHS care must improve, in diagnosis and treatment and put an end to corruption, in the maternity ward and in the pharmacy.

Young people: average age of 20 years and 7 years of schooling, almost all born and residing in this community, all of them of Emakua ethnicity, most Christians, and the rest Muslims; half are single, and the

other half married and equivalent; most of the boys are peasants, others have different activities (student, carpenter, merchant, mechanic).

Men: average age of 50 years and 6 years of schooling, half were born and live in this community, mostly of Emakua ethnicity, all Christians and married or equivalent, all peasants. The health centre (HC) is not able to serve the population and there is often no ambulance to refer the most serious cases to the district capital.

Feedback: the 17 participants (73% male, 35% adolescents and young people) thanked results restitution, hoping the study will bring positive impact. The group evaluated the study method very positively, considering that its objective is in fact to evaluate what they think by feeling included in the process of improving well-being.

Marupa B IDP Community, Chiure District: resettlement centre for IDPs due to violent conflicts in Cabo Delgado, rural hinterland. Chiure is home to 3 resettlement centres, including Marupa B, located 15 km from the municipal town of Chiure. The centre is divided into two neighbourhoods (Josina Machel and Esperança neighbourhoods). Each neighbourhood has 1 leader and 1 assistant secretary, reporting to 1 general head of the camp (organization model according to the guidance of the National Institute for Risk and Disaster Management, NIRDMD), all of them IDPs, men elected and recognized by the IDPs community; their main function is to mediate the support received for IDPs. The general chief works directly with 1 leader of the local native community. All the preparation and data collection activities by the research team took place regularly and the IDPs were enthusiastic about the FGDs. Residents in the camp for an average of 1 year, mostly of Emakua ethnicity, followed by Makonde and Kimwani, most practice the Muslim religion. Men and women have an average schooling of 6 years, the vast majority have no occupation. More than half of adults are married or equivalent, half of women are single.

Women: average age of 43 years and 3 years of schooling, half have lived in this community for 7 years, another half for a year, half are Kimwani, others Makonde and Emakua, most of them Muslim, then Christian and 1 reported not practicing any religion; half are single, and the other half married, 1 is a widow; none have a profession or occupation. Food aid from the World Food Programme (WFP) is not enough. There is no permanent health service, and they suffer from diseases such as malaria, diarrhoea, and influenza; when occasionally the World Health Organization (WHO) "health center" tent has HPs working, it has no medicines.

Youth: average age of 20 years and 5 years of schooling, almost all of them have lived in this community for 1

year, mostly of Emakua ethnicity, others Makondes and Kimwani; most are Muslim and single, others "together" (equivalent to married); most have no occupation, but 5 currently attend school. In their homeland they were peasants, fishermen, shopkeepers, civil servants, but now they do nothing, they receive support from WFP and from their families. Sometimes the mobile health brigade comes, but there are many sick people, they can't take care of all of them.

Men: average age of 57 years and 6 years of schooling, living in this community for 1 year, half are of Emakua ethnicity, half Makonde, most are Muslims, and the others are Christian, all married or equivalent; most have no profession or occupation, 2 are peasants and 2 have positions of local leaders. In this camp there is 1 Elemental Polyvalent Health Agent, but it has no medicines and people are using medicinal plants, when possible, with the help of traditional health practitioners (THPs).

Feedback: the 28 participants (58% female, 57% adolescents and young people), confirmed the information collected, emphasizing the persistence of the reported problems (they do not have hygiene materials to prevent the Covid-19 pandemic). They appreciated the study method verifying information collected veracity, although they expected an immediate positive impact.

Nampula Province

Fishing community, village of Naherenque, municipality of Nacala Porto: on the coast on the south shore of Nacala bay, it is a point of intense transit of people and goods. The neighbourhood of Naherenque (12 km from the port city) in the administrative post of Mutiva, has 1 leader (general secretary of the neighbourhood), 1 head of women's community and another of young people. The men's artisanal fishing activities are varied, and the women and children sweep the bottoms daily, at low tide, collecting crustaceans and bivalves. The participants were almost all of Nahara ethnicity, some Makondes, all Muslims, men, and women with an average education of 8 and 6 years respectively, most adults are married, then single.

Women: average age of 46 years and 5 years of schooling, all born and residing in this community, all of Nahara ethnicity and Muslim; half are married, some single; most are peasants, without specific training. Most women contribute to the family budget with subsistence farming, other domestic works, and 1 traditional midwife. The service at the HC is good in general, they carry out vaccination campaigns and distribute mosquito nets, but it is very small, as well as the maternity ward, where they also make illicit charges and there are often no medicines.

"In the maternity ward, they charge after delivery to take your baby, if you don't pay you

are not allowed to take the baby; they should set a price for childbirth!" (F, 37 years old).

Youth: average age of 20 years and 8 years of schooling, almost all born and residing in this community and of Nahara ethnicity, all Muslims; most are single and 3 are married; most boys are fishermen, 1 is a bricklayer and 1 is a domestic girl. The HC closes very early, it has no emergency service, it has no water, it cannot respond to the demand of many people, HPs diverts medicines.

Men: average age of 44 years and 7 years of schooling, almost all born and residing in this community, all of Nahara ethnicity and Muslim religion; most are married and 5 singles. They are all fishermen. There are many cases of malaria, hypertension, diabetes, but then there are no drugs in the HC. The situation improved because a private pharmacy has now opened, but you must have money; the HC does not have water, what hygiene to prevent Covid-19?

Feedback: the 29 participants (56% female, 38% adolescents and young people) confirmed the information collected and wanted to reinforce some complaints: HC without physical and human conditions. The group positively evaluated the study method, considering that the collection of information in the population is much more realistic than that transmitted by the leaders.

Muslim community, municipality of Mozambique Island: this city was the first capital of Mozambique, classified as a World Heritage Site, it is densely populated by a population of Nahara ethnicity, mostly Muslim; men and women with an average schooling of 7 years and 9 years respectively; most adults are married, there are also widowed women.

Women: average age of 44 years and 9 years of schooling, all born and residing in this community, all of Nahara ethnicity and Muslim; most are married and 3 are widows. Most women are traders. The hospital does not have the necessary conditions or sufficient services, there are not enough rooms and no power generator (there are many cuts in the Mozambican electricity network, they watch births by candlelight), the care is of low quality, medicines are often lacking, there are illicit charges and often it is not able to transfer serious patients.

Youth: average age of 17 years and 9 years of schooling, all born and residing in this community, all of Nahara ethnicity, of Muslim religion, single and students (boys and girls). Health is good, but it is necessary to improve the professionalism of the HPs, they must respect patients, provide the necessary medicines, and put an end to illicit charges.

Males: average age of 46 years and 6 years of schooling, almost all born and residing in this community, all of Nahara ethnicity and Muslim; most are married and 2 are single. Most are fishermen, some are traders. The hospital works badly, it no longer has a

vaccination campaign, it should have an X-ray and surgery service and eliminate illicit drug charges.

Feedback: the 27 participants (57% male, 22% adolescents and young people) confirmed the information collected but have high expectations about study results impact. The group appreciated the study method, considering that the collection of information in the population is more realistic than that transmitted by the leaders.

Community of IDPs of Corrane, Meconta district: with a native population of 34,980 inhabitants (2017), the district received 20,211 IDPs in February 2021. The camp is a permanent accommodation centre and by July 2021, 1,250 families were settled (6,810 people, 3,025 females, 284 in vulnerable groups), mostly of Makonde ethnicity, but also Emakua and Kimwani, mostly Christians (80%). The Nampula provincial government manages this centre, supported by the NIRD and the administrative post of Corrane. The centre has 1 coordinator who works with the head of the post and the commander of the police centre.

Women: average age of 54 years and 2 years of schooling, living in the camp for an average of 6 months, mostly of Maconde ethnicity (1 Kimwani, 1 Emakua, 1 Yawo), mostly Christian (4 Muslim), all without a profession and almost all without an occupation, half are single and less than half married. Their health is not good, they sleep on the floor, there is no soap for hygiene. Health services should be improved by empowering HPs, who should be adults and experienced and who should work full-time.

Youth: average age of 22 years and 7 years of schooling, resident in this community for an average of 6 months, almost all of them of Maconde ethnicity (also Emakua), most are Christians, 1 Muslim and 1 have no religion; half are married, and the others are single. Boys and girls have no occupation. Fortunately, their health is good, because when they go to the temporary HC, there are no medicines.

Men: living in the camp for an average of 9 months, with an average age of 43 years and 7 years of schooling, mostly of Makonde ethnicity, then Kimwani and Emakua; almost all married (1 single) and without a job (2 are peasants and 1 is the head of the camp). They feel sick, traumatized, discriminated against, they sleep on the floor in precarious living conditions; they have chronic diseases, but without treatment, because at the HC the HPs divert the medicines. They ask for quality water, a variety of food, mosquito nets and personal hygiene products.

Feedback: the 14 participants (67% female, 36% adolescents and young people) confirmed the information collected and did not want to add anything, other than reinforcing the issue of lack of food, a threat to the health of IDPs. They appreciated the method of

the study, but criticized the delay in the return of the results and did not give further comment.

Niassa Province

Urban community of Sanga district: in an isolated inland rural environment, the small town of Unango was the first village elevated to the category of city after Mozambique's independence. All participants are of Jawa ethnicity and profess the Islamic religion, are members or sympathizers of the Mozambique Liberation Front (FRELIMO) party. Subsistence farming is the basic activity and there are occasionally seasonal wage jobs. In relation to health, most feel well, but threatened by the pandemic, the uncontrolled evolution of diseases, the lack of resources in the NHS, illicit collections, mosquitoes, malaria, human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection, cholera, lack of individual and collective hygiene. The way to guarantee health would be to improve the professionalism and technical capacity of HPs, as well as their working conditions and the availability of medicines in quantity and quality.

Women: average age of 52 years and 2 years of schooling, almost all born and residing in this community, all Jawa ethnicity and Muslim; most are married (2 divorced, 1 widow and 1 single), almost all are peasants, but 5 are also THPs. They lament the lack of water and energy in the HC.

Youth: average age of 25 years and 9 years of schooling (8 for girls), almost all born and residing in this community, all Jawa ethnicity and Muslim; most are together or married (2 girls separated and 1 single). The girls are mostly peasants, but 2 are attending school; boys are also mostly peasants, but 3 are motorbike taxi drivers and 1 shopkeeper.

Men: average age of 52 years and 5 years of schooling, almost all born and living in this community, all of them of Jawa ethnicity, of Muslim religion and married.

Feedback: the 23 participants (53% female, 17% adolescents and young people), confirmed results restitution and wanted to add that they did not have a Covid-19 vaccination campaign. The group evaluated the study positively, encouraging new interventions and considering that it helped to reflect on the problems and find solutions. They hope the study will bring a positive impact and were grateful for results restitution allowing them to confirm what they said in FGD.

Rural community of Mecula, Niassa Reserve: inland rural area in Mozambique's largest nature reserve, near the border with Tanzania. Participants of Jawa ethnicity profess Islam, adult men, and women with an average schooling of 6 years. Most households live off subsistence farming, supported by small trade and small informal businesses. As for health, most are doing well, but they feel the threat of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. Health threats are the lack of resources in

the NHS, HIV infection, lack of individual and collective hygiene. They use public services when necessary and if available, but there has been a lot of criticism about the practice of corruption, favouritism and clientelism. HCs distribute mosquito nets and condoms.

Women: average age of 48 years and 4 years of schooling, almost all born and residing in this community and of Jawa ethnicity (1 Emakua), of Muslim religion (1 Christian), half married or equivalent, 2 divorced, 2 widows and 1 single. They are all peasants. There is a perception that diseases increase uncontrollably and require HCs with sufficient resources. They report poor service in public services and illegal charges.

Young people: average age of 25 years and 11 years of schooling, almost all born and residing in this community, mostly of Jawa ethnicity (4 Emakua) and Muslim religion (2 Christians) and married or equivalent. Almost half are shopkeepers, 3 girls are students, 1 boy is a peasant and 1 is a domestic worker; some young men also practice fishing and mining. They complain about poor public services due to "clientelism", favouritism, poor service, corruption, illicit charges, and various arbitrary acts.

"...in HC these days there are many complaints, it is normal for me to be serious and to see another who is known, to be attended before you who arrived first" (F, 24 years old).

Men: average age of 58 years and 4 years of schooling, almost all born and living in this community, of Jawa ethnicity (3 Emakua), of Muslim religion (1 Christian) and all married. Most are peasants, 1 merchant, 3 local leaders and 1 THP.

Feedback: the 16 participants (60% male, 69% adolescents and young people) confirmed the results. The group has positively evaluated the study method, believing that some of the improvements that occurred in the field are its results; they welcomed the initiative and are privileged to be part of it.

Conclusion

Mozambique is a country with a developing economy that is still very fragile, and the three northern provinces are historically the most neglected and disadvantaged. This study illustrates the data from the Human Development Report 2020, in which Mozambique is ranked 181st out of 189 countries evaluated [12]. The data processing complied with UN guidelines on language used in matters related to conflict and humanitarian responses [13]. The stratification by gender and age group of participants in the FGDs demonstrates a coherence of social perceptions about the issues under analysis in these communities.

Perception of determinants of individual and community health

Young people are in good health, although threatened by the Covid-19 pandemic and "drug" abuse. They recognize the benefit of free NHS services but complain about the poor quality of care. Women are not in good health, they have the perception that there are more diseases evolving in an uncontrolled way, many without effective treatment, due to poor water quality, lack of food and poor quality or non-existent medicines. In the resettlement camps, tents and mobile brigades have been set up to provide health care, but these are irregular, with few or no medicines. Health is not improving, physically and psychologically, because there are many old and new diseases, in the NHS the physical conditions and care are not of quality, with weak reference capacity and there is corruption. In the IDPs communities there are many chronically ill people without treatment and traumatized by the conflict, the NHS mobile brigade is not able to attend everyone, and people resort to medicinal plants (THPs). Considering as health threats violent conflicts, the Covid-19 pandemic and other new diseases, household solid waste without adequate treatment, theft, and diversion of medicines in the NHS, abnormal movement of foreign people; in the Niassa Reserve, the main threat is the human-wildlife conflict, and they propose the installation of electric fences in protection zones. Communities know how to improve their health: health education, healthy eating, good quality water, individual and community hygiene, sanitation, protected sexual relations, reducing alcohol consumption and misinformation, improving NHS services, expanding physical infrastructure, improving care, diagnosis, and referral, with ethical and technically trained HPs, providing quality medicines, eliminating corruption, distributing mosquito nets and calcium hypochlorite to disinfect water and vegetables. The IDP communities reported they need to diversify the food it receives, a HC with permanent HPs and properly supplied with medicines, with the capacity to refer and transport to the hospital when necessary.

Feedback

The return of results to the communities received a general approval and confirmed the information recorded. The number of participants did not reach the total FGDs participants, due to scheduling issues, maintaining, however, the proportion of strata (men, women, adolescents, and young people) and reinforcing the main ideas collected. It also revealed the participants' expectations regarding the practical impact of this study.

The health of people in civil society-based communities in Cabo Delgado, Nampula and Niassa provinces is threatened by local, regional, national, and global determinants beyond their control. This situation is aggravated for females and can be considered critical for IDPs. In these provinces, people face an

unfavourable systemic context, in conditions of low economic level and restricted consumption. The low standard of living felt by civil society in general seems to result from the deterioration of economic activity, public services, and health. The conflicts and the pandemic have also had a very negative impact on the northern region of the country.

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